

Evaluation of the Metal-Based Nanoparticles on Microbial Growth

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ABSTRACT

Nanomaterials are the centre of the exponentially growing area of nanotechnology. One of the most difficult challenges in current nanotechnology is developing accurate experimental techniques for the synthesis of nanomaterials with a wide range of chemical compositions, sizes, and high monodispersity. This feature of nanotechnology is critical in the present drive to develop green technologies for material creation. Biological systems, masters of ambient condition chemistry, produce inorganic compounds that are arranged in a hierarchical manner from the nano to the macroscale. Recent research on the use of microbes in nanoparticle manufacturing is a fascinating and promising area of study. This study presents a brief outline of current global research on the use of microorganisms (bacteria, actinobacteria, algae, yeast and fungi) in the production of metal nanoparticles and their applications.

Keywords: Nanomaterials, nanotechnology, green technologies, monodispersity, microorganisms

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a branch of science that deals with nano-scale particles. Currently, nanotechnology in medicine has advanced to the point where nanoparticles can be incorporated into medical devices, thereby boosting treatment effectiveness (Golla N., 2025). Metals have been used since ancient times to treat infections, with metal nanoparticles gaining traction as antimicrobial agents due to their effectiveness against bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Silver nanoparticles have received significant focus for their antimicrobial properties, but other nanoparticles, such as gold, zinc oxide, titanium oxide, copper oxide, and magnesium oxide, also show antibacterial effects. These metal nanoparticles can induce oxidative stress and damage microbial cells' proteins, DNA, and membranes. They may also serve as carriers for antimicrobial medications, broadening their potential applications (Brandelli et al., 2017). Characterisation methods such as UV spectroscopy, NMR, and FTIR are used to obtain molecular identification and structural information. Chromatography techniques like column chromatography, HPLC, and GC are essential for

separating and analysing the structure of nanoparticles (Sandhya Rani et al 2025). Nanomaterials are a forefront topic in nanotechnology, addressing challenges such as synthesising materials with diverse chemical compositions and sizes while ensuring high monodispersity. This is crucial in the pursuit of sustainable green technologies. Biological systems effectively synthesise inorganic materials that are hierarchically organised from the nanoscale to the macroscale. Recent research on microorganisms for nanoparticle synthesis represents a promising and innovative area in this field (Mandal et al 2006). Organisms can provide inorganic materials both intracellularly and extracellularly. Unicellular organisms such as magnetotactic bacteria synthesise magnetite nanoparticles (Dickson, 1999), while diatoms produce siliceous materials (Kroger, 1999). Multicellular organisms create hard composite materials such as bones and shells, consisting of inorganic components and organic matrices that shape these structures (Lowen Stam, 1981). Surface-layer bacteria generate gypsum and calcium carbonate (Pum et al 1999). Microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi, are being explored as eco-friendly nano

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factories for biotechnological applications such as toxic metal remediation and the biosynthesis of nanomaterials, representing a novel research area (Sastry et al., 2004). In this article, a brief overview is provided on current global research regarding the use of microorganisms, including bacteria, actinomycetes, algae, yeast, and fungi, in the biosynthesis of metal nanoparticles and their applications.

Biosynthesis of metal nanoparticles by wild-type microorganisms

Bacteria

Bacteria were the first microorganisms used in early experiments on metal nanoparticle manufacturing because of their relative ease of cultivation and manipulation (Lee et al. 1996). Furthermore, most initial studies focused on the synthesis of gold nanoparticles. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Cupriavidus metallidurans*, *Shewanella algae*, *Rhodopseudomonas capsulata*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Shewanella oneidensis* have all been employed to synthesize gold nanoparticles. In most of these experiments, bacterial cells were treated with gold chloride solution, resulting in the formation of nanoparticles ranging from 5-200 nm in diameter. (Beveridge and Murray 1980, Park et al., 2016). Depending on the experimental conditions, gold ion precursors converted into nanoparticles either intracellularly or extracellularly. Microbial reduction of gold ions produced nanoparticles with octahedral, triangular, hexagonal, and spherical shapes, which are similar to the typical geometries of gold nanoparticles generated by standard chemical synthetic methods (Beveridge and Murray 1980, Duman et al., 2024). Furthermore, bacterial reduction of gold ions can occur via environmental bioremediation mechanisms in metallophilic bacteria, such as *C. metallidurans* (Rea et al. 2016), which is critical for metal cycling and mineralisation in metal-enriched environments. Bacteria can also produce other metal nanoparticles. Interestingly, silver ions, which are considered to be highly poisonous to most microbial organisms, may be reduced and converted into silver nanoparticles utilising bacteria (Singh et al. 2008). Bacteria, including *Lactobacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, isolated from a silver mine, were employed to

synthesize silver nanoparticles with a well-defined size and structure (Tiquia-Arashiro et al., 2016). Co, Cu, CuO, CdS, Co₃O₄, Fe₃S₄, Fe₃O₄, Hg, Li, Ni, Pb, Pd, Pt, Rh, Se, Te, PbS, and ZnS are the inorganic metal nanoparticles synthesized using bacteria and photosynthetic cyanobacteria (Aiking et al., 1982; Akçay et al., 2017). Additionally, magnetic nanowires have been synthesized during the pili formation process of *Geobacter* sp. (Lovley et al., 2019).

Actinobacteria

Actinomycetes are another bacterial family that can synthesise several types of metal nanomaterials. Gold nanoparticles were synthesised by using *Thermomonospora* sp. and *Rhodococcus* sp. (Ahmad et al., 2003b; Mazhari et al., 2024). To synthesise gold nanoparticles using Actinobacteria, the nanoparticles exhibit triangular, hexagonal, and spherical shapes, with diameters of 5-50 nm (Manivasagan et al., 2016). Magnetotactic bacteria have been used to produce magnetic nanoparticles, including Fe₃S₄, FeS₂, Fe₃O₄, γ-Fe₂O₃, and FeS₂ (Mann et al. 1984; Bansal et al 2012; Papaefthymiou et al., 2014). Among these metal nanomaterials, Fe₃S₄ and FeS₂ were produced extracellularly under aerobic conditions by reacting a ferric source with an exogenous sulfate source (Bharde et al. 2008).

Yeast

Several publications have demonstrated that all yeast genera have the ability to accumulate various heavy metals. They can accumulate large amounts of highly toxic metals. Enzymatic oxidation or reduction, sorption at the cell wall and, in some cases, subsequent chelation with extracellular peptides or polysaccharides, controlled cell membrane transport of heavy metals towards or active efflux from the cell are the various mechanisms developed by these species to overcome the toxic effects of heavy metals. Yeast cells require strict management of internal metal ions in order to avoid adverse consequences. The synthesis of nanoparticles in yeast varies due to size, location, and properties, influenced by detoxification mechanisms involving glutathione (GSH) and metal-binding ligands (Jha et al., 2016). Yeasts are recognized for synthesizing semiconductor nanoparticles, notably cadmium sulfide (CdS) and lead sulfide (PbS) (Jacob et al., 2016). For example,

Pichia jadinii synthesizes gold nanoparticles through the reduction of gold ions. Yeasts such as *Candida glabrata* form quantum crystallites in cadmium salts, while silver-tolerant strains like MKY3 produce silver nanoparticles via secreted biochemical reducing agents (Shah et al., 2015). *Yarrowia lipolytica* demonstrates resistance to heavy metals and is utilized for both bioremediation and nanoparticle synthesis (Bankar et al., 2018). Additionally, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* is known for cadmium and lead biosorption, facilitating nanomaterial production. Overall, while most yeast species can synthesize nanoparticles, notable exceptions exist.

Fungi

Fungi can also be utilized to produce a wide range of inorganic metal nanoparticles. Gold nanoparticles can be produced by exposing *Verticillium sp.* and *Fusarium oxysporum* to AuCl₄⁻ ions (Subashini et al., 2018). In this research, transmission electron microscopy revealed that when gold nanoparticles were generated near the cell walls, yellow-colored fungal cells turned purple. Similarly, *Verticillium sp.* cells were exposed to an aqueous AgNO₃ solution to produce silver nanoparticles with a diameter of around 25 nm (Das et al 2011). Silver nanoparticles were found primarily at the cell surface and internal cell borders, suggesting that cell walls may act as nucleation sites. *F. oxysporum* has been reported to produce a wide range of metal nanoparticles, including Ag, Au-Ag, CdS, CdSe, Co₃O₄, SiO₂, TiO₂, ZrO₂, BaTiO₃, Bi₂O₃, and Fe₃O₄ (Sharma et al., 2019). These fungi were simply exposed to solutions containing various metals or inorganic ions to synthesise different types of metal nanoparticles.

Algae

Nanotechnology is being used to treat algae, another varied group of plants. The dried cell suspension of *Chlorella vulgaris* accumulated elemental Au ranging in size from 9 to 20 nm (Hosea et al., 1986). *P. boryanum*, a filamentous cyanobacterium, was employed to synthesize gold nanoparticles. It is demonstrated to give control over the form of gold nanoparticles. Cyanobacteria in aqueous gold (III) chloride solution precipitated amorphous gold (I)-sulfide nanoparticles on their cell walls. Metallic gold

was deposited as octahedral platelets (~10 nm to 6 μm) on cell surfaces and in liquids. The XAS (X-ray absorption spectroscopy) investigation revealed that cyanobacteria reduce gold (III)-chloride to metallic gold, forming an intermediate Au (I) species and gold (I)-sulfide (Bhardwaj et al., 2021). A marine alga, *Sargassum wightii greville*, demonstrated fast extracellular production of Au nanoparticles ranging in size from 8 to 12 nm (Singaravelu et al., 2007). Bio-reduction with *Fucus vesiculosus*, an alternative, environmentally benign technology, can recover Au from dilute hydrometallurgical solutions and electronic scrap leachates.

Viruses

Biogenic nanoparticles are environmentally friendly, rapidly created in high quantities, biocompatible, and have well-defined size and shape (Duan et al 2015). Several factors influence the size, shape, nucleation, and stability of biogenic nanoparticles. These parameters include pH, temperature, reactant concentration, and synthesis time (Velgosova et al 2025). Metal NPs can be produced by microorganisms both intracellularly and extracellularly. Metal ions, for example, are enzymatically reduced into intracellularly and extracellularly produced NPs after being carried into the microbial cell and trapped on the cell surface (Pantidos et al 2014). Plant-based viruses, including cowpea chlorotic mottle virus (CCMV), cowpea mosaic virus (CPMV), brome mosaic virus (BMV), and tobacco mosaic virus (TMV), are utilized as biological templates to create nanomaterials. Plant viruses are suitable for nanomaterial synthesis due to their small size, symmetric structure, ease of functionalization, monodispersity, and self-assembling capacity. Plant viruses are not contagious to people or animals (Zhang et al 2018). Biological extracts from the leaves, flowers, stems, seeds, and roots of numerous plant species are also thought to be safe and environmentally benign for metal NP production. In plant extracts, existing metabolites (e.g., sugars, terpenoids, alkaloids, phenolic acids, proteins) are predominantly responsible for metal ion bioreduction and the generation of stable NPs (Shah et al 2015). To avoid environmental toxicity, cytotoxicity, and carcinogenicity, biological techniques are preferable (Ai, J., Biazar et al 2011).

Fig 1. The Metal-Based Nanoparticles on Microbial Growth.

Future Prospective

In future prospective, a brief overview of the application of microorganisms such as *bacteria*, *actinomycetes*, *yeasts*, *algae*, *fungi*, and *viruses* in the production of metal nanoparticles has been addressed. "Bio-nanotechnology" is an interdisciplinary field that necessitates collaboration among physicists, chemists, biologists and engineers. A case has been made for conducting substantial research on microbes as an alternative to the more widely used physical and chemical methods. Several challenges must be addressed from the perspectives of nanotechnology and microbiology before such biosynthetic processes can compete with standard protocols. The identification of metabolic pathways leading to metal ion reduction in various microbial classes is required for the development of a rational microbial nanoparticle production technique. The surface chemistry of biogenic nanoparticles should be precisely identified. Genetic engineering approaches might be utilized to increase particle characteristics and alter their composition. The transition from bacteria to fungi as a technique of generating natural "nanofactories" has the added benefit of making downstream processing and management of the biomass significantly simpler. At the moment, microbiological approaches for the production of nanomaterials of different compositions are extremely limited, confined to metal, some metal sulfides, and very few oxides. An extension of the processes to

allow for the reliable synthesis of nanocrystals of additional oxides (TiO_2 , ZrO_2 , etc.), nitrides, carbides, and so on could make microbial synthesis commercially viable.

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